

Original Research Article

Perceived Factors Militating against Sustainable Green Practices in Selected Hotels in Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

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Globally, sustainability is a demand in all phases of human daily need. All sectors of human activities including hotel facilities and services require a sustainable approach to achieve a friendly and sustainable environment. The study evaluated the perceived factors militating against the establishment and adoption of sustainable green practices in selected hotels in Ondo- State. Structured questionnaires were used to collect data, a total of 220 were purposively administered in the twenty (20) selected hotels, where each hotel manager and ten guests were selected for the study. The data obtained were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics; the result shows that there was no policy sustaining the use and recycling process in the selected hotels (3.00) and the need for training of staff and guest for effective handling of green practices facilities (4.70) and incompetence of the hotel staff with modern green practices will affect the hotel business (4.50). The study concluded that there is absence of prescribed legislation or policy, certification for sustainable green practices, hence it is necessary for hotel employee to be trained and retrained. Furthermore, it is recommended that sustainable green practices should be integrated more into the hotel facilities and used as standard for hotel licensing this will ensure sustainable environment and conservation of our natural resources.

Keywords: Green Practices, Hotel facilities and environment, Sustainable Development,

INTRODUCTION

Going green or green practice is a portion of everyday action that is intentionally considered to ensure reuse or conservation of resources for future use (Adegbola and Arowosafe 2022). It is the process of transforming and preserving something for future use. According to the United Nations World Organization (UNWTO, 2015a), hotels are one of the fastest growing service sectors and the technologies used in the hotel industry have been effective in marketing, booking, room service, communication, billing and payment. Hotels are part of tourism industry; exert a significant impact on the environment, while the extent and range of the impact that hotels exert on the environment, suggest an urgent need to address this problem. The question that arises is

whether hoteliers appreciate the need for environmentally-friendly initiatives in their establishments (Mbasera et al., 2016). According to Christina, Chee and Sakun (2016) Green practices are considered to be environmentally responsible mediums that reduce human ecological footprint or demand on natural resources and ecosystems in which humans coexist. The global challenges include; poverty, inequality, climate, environmental degradation, prosperity, peace and justice are as a result of improper sustainable measures especially in the African nations (United Nations, 2017). Also, Greening lodging has enormous benefits. It meets consumer demand and increases satisfaction. Many consumers are interested in green lifestyles and green

tourism. In fact, marketers realize that the fastest growing target markets are Lifestyles of Health and Sustainability (LOHAS) and Naturalists (Mbasera, 2015). Green practice is the hope for a sustainable ecosystem for future generations. According to Abisuga and Oyekanmi (2014) the practice of sustainability in building hotel facilities is paramount to the preservation of the built environment which is lacking in Nigeria. Lack of awareness and knowledge of construction personnel, cost and economic ability, passive culture or norm, top management commitment, organizational goal and objectives were the internal organizational factors militating against the green practice. While the external factors militating against the practice were research and development, Knowledge and skill of personnel, learning period, local authority and government (Abidin, 2010; Abisuga et al., 2014).

Currently there are miniature green-certified lodging or hotel properties in Nigeria. There is budding apprehension for a 'green' hotel in the view of guests as they experience an increased awareness of environmental damage and excessive consumption of goods, energy, water and others (Mbasera et al., 2016). According to Ladi et al. (2017) the high level of awareness of sustainable practices around the globe and green practices literature on its adoption in hotel businesses have few studies. Mbasera (2015) green management framework for hotels in South Africa and Zimbabwe so that developing countries may contribute significantly in mitigation of the negative environmental effects. Ladi et al. (2017) studied the predictors of likelihood of adoption of green practices in hotels in Abuja and Lagos, Nigeria for environmental management and sustainable development. Ibrahim (2019) studied innovation networks as a tool for food-culture preservation and sustainability in the era of globalization while, Franzisca et al. (2019) stated problem of water supply, abuse of environmental discourses and natural resources and Adegbola et al., 2022 stated that guest's awareness of sustainable green practices.

Energy efficiency is utilizing energy to prevent excessive penetration into synthetic sources for the benefit of the human environment. According to Hsieh (2012), to increase energy efficiency, green hotels have to implement measures to reduce energy consumption during operation especially during the daylight hours. Hotel facilities required an approach to protect, enhance or reduce its impacts on its environment by setting objectives, targets and developing programmes and activities for sustainable environment which are audited and evaluated (Hoegh-Guldberg et al. 2018). Conserving energy reduces greenhouse gases, pollutants, and the use of natural resources, and saves money. Energy saving options to consider is lighting, heating and cooling, building materials and other appliances used for hospitality services (Lisa 2019).

Water is essential for all forms of life and crucial for human development. Water systems, coastal zones, surface waters and aquifers provide a vast majority of environmental goods and services, including drinking water, transport and food (Akinwalere et al., 2020). Water management and water conservation is the activity of planning, developing, distributing and optimum use of water resources under defined water policies and regulations. Cosgrove and Loucks (2015) posited that there is a need to advance the global monitoring information system on water to provide the information needed for water management and to monitor progress against targets. Lodging properties used an average of 218 gallons of water each day for each guest room. Water-efficient plumbing fixtures can reduce water and sewer costs by 25-30 percent (Londoño et al., 2016). A single hotel purchases more products in one-week than 100 families do in a year (Lisa, 2019). Each room produces as much as 30 pounds of waste each day. Yixiu, et al. (2016) American Hotels and Lodging Association, in 2012 stated that the USA hotels spent \$8.2 billion on energy, created 7 million tons of waste, consumed 64 trillion gallons of water, and generated 23 million tons of CO₂ also in California, hotels alone generate 112,000 tons of food waste each year. The room toiletries such as soaps and shampoos can be bought in bulk and placed in pump dispensers attached to shower walls and sinks. This reduces costs, production, and waste from disposing of individual containers. (Masson-Delmotte et al., 2018). In addition, food bought locally supports local farmers and reduces the energy used for transportation, while enriching the local people. Office waste can be reduced by encouraging people to avoid printing unnecessarily and to print or copy on both sides of the paper. One hundred percent (100%) of post-consumer materials are to be made recyclable. Building materials can be purchased from renewable materials. Cork and rubber are environmentally friendly and are low in contaminants that reduce indoor air quality. Carpet tiles also are environmentally friendly because stained and worn areas can be replaced without replacing the entire carpeted area. According to Rob (2019) about 30 percent of waste in hotels can be diverted through reuse and recycling and identified that *hotels are not only resource intensive but that waste generation is one of the most visible effects on the environment identified that an average hotel produces in excess of one kilogram of waste per guest per day.*

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

This research was conducted in Ondo State, Nigeria. Twenty hotels were selected in the populated town, representing 13% of all hotels in Ondo State

Figure 1. Map of Ondo State; Showing Owo, Idanre, Akure and Oke-Igbo

Source: Field Work 2021.

covering the three senatorial districts were chosen for this study. These well populated towns were targeted for influx of the guest to ensure the hotels rated range was 2 to 4 stars according to National tourism board, Ondo State chapter, (20-50) number of rooms which determine the influx of the guest with restaurant capacity of about (50) constitutes to quantity waste disposal and maximum of (5 to 15) years of operation determine the period of time that green facilities has been adopted in the selected hotels. The obtained data was analysed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation in SPSS Version 20 and the results are presented in form mean value and percentages.

Methods of Data Collection and Analysis

The primary data were; field observations, field surveys, structured questionnaires and interviews while secondary data was from; books, journals, and hotel documents respectively. In this study data were from hotels in four towns (Owo, Akure, Idanre, and Oke-Igbo) covering three senatorial districts, three Local Government Areas (Ose, Akure South(s), and Ile-Oluji/Oke-Igbo). Figure 1

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The table 1.0 respondents (hotel manager), shows the result of the findings on perceived factors militating against sustainable green practices in their hotels. The result revealed that the cost of installation sustainable green practice under which were purchased from environmentally responsible/organic sources is expensive (3.40). This is supported Mbasera *et al.* (2016) stated that green or eco-friendly facilities in the hotel industry are also on the rise across the world, and customers are becoming more aware of the need for eco-friendly services. The result obtained also revealed that there are lack of effective regulation or policy and certification for sustainable green practices in the hotel, that is, no policy sustaining the use and recycling process in the selected hotels. This is supported by Fakorede, Anguruwa and Ajayi (2020) who emphasized the place of policy in the sustainable eco-environment and Adegbola *et al.* (2022) determine guests' awareness of sustainable green practices in the selected hotels, Incompetence or need for training which are; training for staff and guest for effective handling of green practices facilities (4.70) and effect the hotel business (4.50). This is attested to the fact that perceived factors militating against

Table 1. Perceived Factors Militating against Hotel Establishment and adoption of Sustainable Green Practices in their hotels.

S/N	Variables	SA	A	InD.	D	SD	Mean (X)	St.Div	Rank
Costly Installation									
1.	Purchase from environmentally responsible/organic sources is expensive.	0	8(40%)	12(60%)	0	0	3.400	0.503	1
2	Costs for technocrats or experts for green practices are on the high side.	0	0	4(20%)	16(80%)	0	2.200	0.410	2
3	Retention of Biodiversity and hotel facilities are costly	0	0	3(15%)	15(75%)	2(10%)	2.050	0.510	3
4	Installation of the recycling water process in the hotel is expensive?	0	0	1(5%)	18(90%)	1(5%)	2.000	0.324	4
Ineffective Regulation and Certification									
5	Reuse of plastics, towel, cutleries, and beddings required certification.	0	1(5%)	18(90%)	1(5%)	0	3.000	0.394	1
6	Conservation of birds, butterflies and natural fixtures are part of hotel certification.	0	0	0	11(55%)	9(45%)	1.550	0.510	2
7	Eco-friendly retails/e-transact is a compelled is difficult to acquire.	0	0	0	10(50%)	10(50%)	1.500	0.510	3
8	Eco-friendly interior decoration and fittings in the hotel are regulated	0	0	0	4(20%)	16(80%)	1.200	0.410	4
Incompetence and Need for Training									
9	Required training for staff and guests for effective handling of green practices facilities.	14(70%)	6(30%)	0	0	0	4.700	0.489	4
10	Stress of guiding the Guest/ Tourist on green facilities can be worrisome.	6(30%)	10(50%)	4(20%)	0	0	4.100	0.752	1
11	Training and re-training of hotel staff and guests can be worrisome.	12(60%)	7(35%)	1(5%)	0	0	1.4500	0.605	3
12	Incompetency of the hotel staff with green practices will affect the hotel business.	12(60%)	6(30%)	2(10%)	0	0	4.500	0.688	2
Lack of Awareness.									
13	Local interior decoration (Window mat, Can chair) is part of green practices.	0	0	10(50%)	5(25%)	5(25%)	2.250	0.851	2
14	Urban forestry is part green practices.	0	0	8(40%)	11(55%)	1(5%)	2.350	0.587	3
15	Green practices in hotels prevent guests from patronage.	0	0	0	15(75%)	5(25%)	1.750	0.444	4
16	Eco-friendly landscaping in the hotel harbors dangerous reptiles.	2(10%)	9(45%)	3(15%)	5(25%)	1(5%)	3.300	1.129	1

Scale and symbol codes: SA = strongly agree (5); A = agree(4); InD= Indifference (3), D = disagree(2) SD = strongly disagree(1); x=Mean. The desired mean score values ($x \geq 2.50$).

Source: Field Work 2021

green practices in the selected hotels were miniature. The factors militating against the Sustainable green practice were ranked according to their effect (Table 1.0)

The Perceived factors militating against green practices in selected hotels are purchase from environmentally responsible/organic sources which were not encouraged by guest, regulation or policy on certification for sustainable green practices were ineffective and there is need for training and retraining of staff to ensure use of the green facilities in the hotel, this is supported by Abisuga *et al.* (2014) stated that the practice of sustainability in building hotel facilities is paramount to the preservation of the built environment which is lacking in Nigeria. Likewise, there is deficiency of awareness and knowledge of construction personnel, cost and economic ability, passive culture or norm, top management commitment, organizational goal and objectives were the internal organizational factors militating against the green practice. While the external factors militating against the practice were research and development, Knowledge and skill of personnel, learning period, and local authority and government (Abidin, 2010; Abisuga *et al.*, 2014). Additionally, Rob (2019) reported that efforts are being made in the hotel industry to improve green practices with implementation of linen and towel reuse programs, installation of low-flow faucets, showerheads, and other fixtures; recycling and waste reduction with the limited exception for domestic hotels, recycling programs for basics such as newspapers and beverage containers as shown in table 1.

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CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The results of the study revealed the perceived barriers to the introduction and acceptance of sustainable green

practices in hotels, including the absence of formal legislation or policy, certification for sustainable green practices, and the necessity for hotel employee training and retraining. It is recommended that, there should be formal legislation or policy, certification for sustainable green practices, and the necessity for hotel employee training and retraining .

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